

PRODUCTION AND MARKETING PATTETRN OF ORANGE IN KOHIMA DISTRICT OF NAGALAND

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ABSTRACT

Agriculture continues to dominate the work sector in India with over 65.00 per cent of the population depending on agriculture for their livelihood as the primary source of income. It is the backbone of the Indian economy and with the majority of the population belonging to the rural sector; agriculture holds a central place in the rural economy. The present study was carried out during the agricultural 2023-2024 to investigate the in-depth information of the production and marketing of orange in the selected area of the study. The study was conducted and the data collected through personal interview schedules by the researcher. A total of 100 respondents were selected by following a purposely stratified simple random sampling technique; so four villages from the 2 blocks of the Kohima district were selected for the present study. Further several statistical tools and formulae were used to analyze and interpret the data collected. The sample farmers were divided into groups according to their land holdings and the results concluded based on land holding under the orange crop. The study revealed that a majority of the respondents had small sized farms (0.30 to 1.26 ha) and the yield varied minimum of 1.41 q on marginal farms to maximum of 10.85 q on medium farms, respectively. The study also revealed the cost of cultivation of orange crop was found to be Rs 9,874.00/- per ha on marginal farms, while the cost of cultivation on small and medium farms were recorded as Rs 8,012.00/- and Rs 9,154.00/-, respectively. Whereas the net income was Rs 73,855.00/-, Rs 51,370.60/- and Rs 58,776.26/- on the marginal small and medium farms size groups, respectively. However, the three marketing channels were identified viz; Channel-I was the most prominent or opted channel. The price spread in case of Channel-I was found to be nil, while it was Rs 2,000.00/- and Rs 2,542.10/- on the channel II and III, respectively. The most common production constraint was pest and disease infestation, while it was unavailable storage facilities in case of marketing constraints.

Keywords: Production, Cost, Income, Marketing Channels, Price Spread, Constraints.

INTRODUCTION

Kohima district is the capital of Nagaland with an area of 1,463 km² located at an altitude of 1,444m above MSL. It is situated between 25.6701⁰N and 94.1077⁰E. As per the 2021 census, Kohima had a population of 2,67,988 out of which 1,38,966 were males and 1,29,022 were females. The average rainfall of the district is 2899 mm and witnesses a humid subtropical climate. (Sharma, 2012)a.

Production of fruits and vegetables is important as it gives a steady income to the farmers throughout the year as compared to one time return from field crops and also it generates the income by three to four folds more as compared to other crops. Fruits and vegetables are the primary sources of the crucial minerals and vitamins required for the normal metabolic processes of the human body. The recommended consumption laid down by the ICMR (Indian Council of Medical Research) is 92 grams of fruits per day per head by India only manages to consume 46 grams per capita per day. This is the reason why the country at present is giving importance to the horticultural sector as fruits and vegetables constitute an important requirement for daily nutrition in the body. (Sharma and Sharma, 2019)

Sweet orange (*Citrus sinensis* L. Osbeck) can grow from 7.50 m to 15.00 m in some cases and it is an evergreen tree. It originated from southern China where it has been cultivated for many years, but is today grown commercially worldwide in tropical, semi-tropical and some warm temperate regions to become the most widely planted fruit tree in the world. (Vengoto and Sharma, 2018).

Citrus are one of the most important sources of phytochemicals and are highly valued for their nutrition as well as anti-oxidant properties and has been scientifically proven for their health benefits. Thus, orange is as important as any other crop in terms of nutritive value and is highly recommended to cultivate as well as to consume. (Sharma, 2015)a

The present study attempts to reveal the potentials and constraints in orange production from the farmers' perspectives in Kohima. There is also a need to study in depth the various marketing channels through which the farmers sell their produce, the cost and returns of orange cultivation, price spread, etc. The study will also help to provide feedback to policy makers,

concerned departments and researchers to plan future course of actions for sustainable production of oranges in Kohima, Nagaland. (Sharma, 2016).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Kohima district of Nagaland was purposively selected and the study conducted in the said area. Multistage simple random sampling was used to purposively select the blocks and villages. In the first stage, Kohima district of Nagaland was purposively selected. There is a total of 7 rural development blocks in Kohima. In the second stage, two rural development blocks, namely Kohima block and Chiephobozou block were purposively selected. In the third stage, 4 villages (2 villages from each block) were identified and selected at random. Chedema village and Kohima village were selected from Kohima block. Rusoma village and Meriema village were selected from Chiephobozou block. In the fourth and final stage of the multistage sampling, 25 respondents from each of the 4 villages were selected at random so as to ensure a fair selection and equal probability for each of the farmers. Therefore, a total of 100 respondents were selected and the data was collected accordingly. (Pongener and Sharma, 2018).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1 reveals that the distribution of the population according to the age, gender and marital status. The average age of the respondents was 53.89 years and a maximum number (70.00 per cent) of the respondents were aged between 40 and 67 years. The gender wise distribution of the sample farmers was 79.00 and 2.00 per cent for males and females respectively. On the other hand, majority (92.00 per cent) of the respondents were married as opposed to only 8.00 per cent unmarried ones. Similar finding was also reported in the line by Borah and Sharma (2015).

Table 2 reveals that the maximum number of the respondents had a qualification till high school (46.00 per cent) followed by primary education (31.00 per cent). It was observed that 12.00 per cent of the sample population was illiterate owing to the fact that the study was conducted in villages. A total of 9.00 per cent of the population were graduates and another 2.00 per cent of the population had qualifications higher than a graduate. It was also found that the majority (96.00 per cent) of the sample farmers lived in nuclear family and only 4.00 per cent of

the population lived in a joint family. Similar finding was also reported in the line by Paney and Sharma (2018).

Table 1. Distribution of population according to age, gender and marital status (n = 100)

S. N.	Particulars	Percentage
1.	Age (years)	
	Below 40	11.00
	40 to 67	70.00
	Above 67	19.00
2.	Gender	
	Male	79.00
	Female	21.00
3.	Marital Status	
	Married	92.00
	Unmarried	8.00

Table 2. Distribution of population according to educational qualification of family

(n = 100)

Sl. No.	Particulars	Percentage
1.	Educational qualifications	
	Illiterate	12.00
	Primary	31.00
	High school	46.00
	Graduate	9.00
	Others	2.00
2.	Type of family	
	Joint	4.00

	Nuclear	96.00
3.	Size of family	
	3 members	7.00
	4 members	18.00
	5 members	30.00
	More than 5 members	45.00

Table 3. Distribution of population according to land holdings (n = 100)

Sl. No.	Particulars	Size	Percentage
1.	Marginal	<0.30 ha	20.00
2.	Small	0.30-1.26 ha	67.00
3.	Medium	>1.26 ha	13.00
Total			100.00

Table 3 reveals the number of members in each family of the respondents. Majority (45.00 per cent) of the sample respondents had a family size of more than 5 members while 30.00 per cent of the respondents' family had a size of 5 members. The families with 4 members accounted up to 18.00 per cent of the total population and only 7.00 per cent of the respondents had a family size of 3 members. Similar finding was also reported in the line by Sharma (2014).

Table 4 reveals the costs involved in different categories of farm groups. It was observed that the per ha cost of cultivation was highest in marginal sized farms (Rs 9,874) and the small farm group had the lowest cost of cultivation (Rs 8,012). The cost of cultivation of the small sized farms amounted to Rs 9,154. Similar finding were also reported in the line by Singh and Sharma (2020)d.

Table 4. Cost break up of cost of cultivation of orange orchard (Rs / ha)

Sl. No.	Particulars	Marginal	Small	Medium	Average
1.	i) Family labour	3216	1510	3665	2797.00
	ii) Hired labour	4698	4887	4050	4545.00
2.	Marketing and transportation cost	1960	1615	1439	1617.33
Total cost		9874	8012	9154	9013.33

Table 5. Income of different farm groups

Farm groups	Yield (q/ha)	Price (Rs./q)	Gross income (Rs./ha)	Net income (Rs./ha)
Marginal	8.29	10100.00	83729.00	73855.00
Small	5.69	10418.00	59328.60	51370.60
Medium	6.69	10154.00	67930.26	58776.26

Table 5 reveals that the yield of marginal, small and medium sized groups was 8.29 quintals, 5.69 q and 6.69 q / ha respectively and the price realized for marginal, small and medium farms were Rs 10,100, Rs 10,418 and Rs 10,154 / q, respectively. It was also observed that the gross income for marginal farms was Rs. 83729 / ha, Rs 59,328.6 for small farms and Rs 67,930.26 / ha. The net income for marginal, small and medium sized farms was observed to be Rs 73,855, Rs 51,370.6 and Rs 58,776.26 / ha, respectively. Similar finding was also reported in the line by Tangjang and Sharma (2021).

Table 6 reveals that the percentage of involvement of market intermediaries in the marketing of orange. The study revealed that a majority of the farmers (85.00 per cent) sell their produce directly in the local markets without involving any intermediaries between them and consumers while only a small percentage of the sample farmers (15.00 per cent) sell their

produce to wholesalers and not directly in the market. Similar finding was also reported in the line by Shuya and Sharma (2018).

Table 6. Involvement of market intermediaries (n = 100)

Sl. No.	Particulars	Yes	No
1.	Middlemen involved	15.00	85.00

Table 7 reveals that the various marketing channels adopted by the orange farmers in marketing their produce. It can be understood that the majority (85.00 per cent) of the sample farmers opts for Channel-I as it was the easiest way to sell their produce and which did not involve any market intermediaries. This was followed by channel-III with 14.00 per cent of the farmers adopting the said channel and lastly channel-II was the least opted channel and only 1.00 per cent of the population sold the produce through this channel. Similar finding was also reported in the line by Singh and Sharma (2020)a and Singh and Sharma (2020)a.

Table 7. Channel wise distribution adopted by orange growers (n = 100)

Sl. No.	Marketing channels	% of growers opting
1.	Channel-I	85.00
2.	Channel-II	1.00
3.	Channel-III	14.00

Table 8. Marketing costs incurred in different channels (Rs / qtl)

Sl. No.	Particulars	Channel-I	Channel-II	Channel-III
1.	Transportation	-	140.00	246.78
2.	Loading and unloading	-	125.00	179.63
3.	Quantity loss	-	60.00	71.70
4.	Miscellaneous	-	75.00	57.41
Total			400.00	555.52

Table 8 reveals that the marketing costs incurred in the three channels observed from the study. It can be observed that Channel-I had no marketing cost involved while Channel-II had marketing cost of Rs 400 / q. Since Channel-III had the longest route, the marketing cost was highest in this channel with a total of Rs 555.52 / q. Similar finding was also reported in the line by Sharma (2012)b.

Table 9. Price spread and producer's share in consumer's rupee (Rs / qtl)

Marketing Channels	Producer's net price	Cost incurred by middlemen	Marketing margin	Consumer's price	Price spread	Producer's share in consumer's rupee (%)
Channel-I	10300.46	-	-	10300.46	-	100.00
Channel-II	8000.00	400.00	1600.00	10000.00	2000.00	80.00
Channel-III	9185.18	555.52	1986.57	11727.27	2542.10	78.32

Table 9 reveals the producer's net price varies from Rs 10,300.46 in Channel-I, Rs 8,000 in Channel-II and Rs 985.18 in Channel-III. The price spread of Channel-I was zero which was the lowest observed followed by Channel-II with Rs 2,000 and the highest price spread was observed in Channel-III which amounted to Rs 2,542.10 / ha. It can be also observed from the table that Channel-I had the highest share in consumer's rupee with 100.00 per cent as the share. Channel-II had a producer's share of consumer's rupee of 80.00 per cent and Channel-III had the least with 78.32 per cent, respectively. Similar finding was also reported in the line by Walling and Sharma (2018).

Table 10 reveals that the production constraints faced by the farmer during the production process. It can be seen that the most serious production concern was the infestation by pests and diseases (81.00 per cent of the population faced this constraint) followed by the lack of government support in the production of orange (66.00 per cent) while constraints for low yielding farms were faced by a total of 19.00 per cent of the population. Availability of labour was not a problem for the orange growers as suggested from the study. Similar finding were also reported in the line by Sharma (2015)b.

Table 11. Marketing constraints faced by orange growers (n = 100)

Sl. No.	Constraints	Frequency	Rank
1.	Unavailable storage facilities	54	I
2.	Highly perishable commodity	32	II
3.	Price fluctuation	24	III
4.	Lack of nearby markets	15	IV
5.	Lack of transportation	4	V
6.	High transport cost	1	VI

Table 11 reveals the most serious problem in the marketing of orange is unavailable storage facilities (54.00 per cent) owing to the fact that the study was conducted mostly in rural areas. The second concern for the orange growers was the highly perishable nature of the commodity (32.00 per cent) followed by price fluctuations of orange (24.00 per cent). 15.00 per cent of the population faced difficulties in accessing nearby markets to sell their produce while 4 per cent of the population faced difficulties in transporting their produce. The last rank is occupied by the constraint of high transportation cost where only 1.00 per cent of the population faced the said problem. Similar finding was also reported in the line by Sharma *et al.*, (2018) and Singh and Sharma (2020)b.

CONCLUSION

The majority (67.00 per cent) of the respondents had orchards with an area between 0.03 to 1.26 ha. Average area wise distribution was 0.17 ha, 0.69 ha and 1.62 ha for marginal, small and medium farms, respectively. The average yield accounted to 1.41 q, 3.93 q and 10.85 q for marginal, small and medium farms, respectively. The cost of cultivation / ha was highest in medium farms (Rs 19,154) followed by small farms (Rs 9,194) and marginal farms (Rs 4,100). The net income (Rs / ha) was Rs 73,855, Rs 51,370.6 and Rs 54,776.26 for marginal, small and medium farms, respectively. The major channel identified in the marketing of orange was Channel-I: Producer-Consumer. Only 15.00 per cent of the identified channels had market

intermediaries working. The lowest price spread and highest producer's share in consumer's rupee was found in Channel-I. Pest and disease infestation was the main production constraint while lack of storage facilities ranked first in marketing constraint.

POLICY FOR RECOMMENDATIONS

The following policy recommendations may be worked out based on the above findings:

- As the locale of the present study has high potential for production of oranges, the concerned authority should take relevant measures so as to best exploit the resources and also create employment to the people.
- Seminars and demonstrations should be conducted across orange producing areas so as to make the farmers aware of the latest farm practices and also introduce new scientific interventions for higher yield and productivity.
- Cooled storage facilities should be constructed in the potential growing areas so as to reduce and prevent losses during peak season.
- Processing units for post harvest value added products should be established to prevent wastage especially during the surplus season.
- Farmers should be made known about the management and control of insect pests and diseases as these infestations are the primary reason behind lower productivity.

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